

S32: JBI-inspired risk of bias scores for the 31 included studies

Table 1: JBI-inspired risk of bias scores for the 31 included studies. For questions Q1–Q4 and Q8 the score is 1 (Yes), 0.5 (Unclear), 0 (No) or – (not applicable). Questions Q5, Q6 and Q7 include seven sub-outcomes; the reported value is the arithmetic mean of those sub-scores. Question Q9 involves seven outcomes, each further broken into three sub-results; the reported value is the mean of the per-outcome averages (see text for details). The overall average (Avg.) is the mean of all applicable items.

Study	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Avg.
S1 [47]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.2381	0.9048
S2 [48]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.8571	0.9821
S3 [57]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.0714	0.8839
S4 [58]	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	–	0.0714	0.7589
S5 [59]	1	0	1	–	0	1	1	–	0.1905	0.5986
S6 [60]	1	0	1	–	0.4286	0.4286	0.4286	–	0.0714	0.4796
S7 [50]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.1905	0.8988
S8 [51]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.0408	0.8006
S9 [61]	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	–	0.4286	0.8036
S10 [62]	1	1	1	1	0.7143	0.7143	0.7143	–	0.3571	0.8125
S11 [63]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.4286	0.8286
S12 [64]	1	0	1	–	0	1	1	–	0.2857	0.6122
S13 [65]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.2143	0.9018
S14 [54]	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	–	0.4048	0.8006
S15 [66]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.1667	0.8958
S16 [53]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.1667	0.8958
S17 [67]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.3833	0.7979
S18 [68]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.2619	0.9077
S19 [52]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.2143	0.9018
S20 [22]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.1667	0.8958
S21 [69]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.1667	0.7708
S22 [21]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.1667	0.8958
S23 [70]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.1667	0.8958
S24 [71]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.1905	0.8988
S25 [72]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.1190	0.8899
S26 [73]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.1667	0.8958
S27 [49]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.1905	0.7738
S28 [55]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.2143	0.9018
S29 [56]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.1667	0.8958
S30 [74]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.3333	0.9167
S31 [75]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	–	0.2143	0.9018

Note: Item numbers refer to the list in the main text. For multi-outcome questions the table shows the aggregated average, not a single categorical judgment. Studies with – had no applicable data for that item. Citation numbers are clickable.

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